

TENSILE EVALUATION OF CARBON FOAM LIGAMENTS

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ABSTRACT: The results obtained from the tensile evaluation of single ligaments from SiC and carbon foams are presented. The materials evaluated are two CVD SiC foams with either 20 or 45 pores per inch (PPI), and glassy carbon foam with 20 PPI. The latter is used as the substrate for the densification of the SiC foams. Typical dimensions of the specimens are 0.2 to 0.4 in diameter and 0.75 to 2 mm in length. The procedures for obtaining the ligaments and testing them in tension are described along with the statistical analysis of the results. Ligament isolation consists of separating a single ligament from the unit cell of ceramic foam, which requires rigorous and challenging sequence of preparatory step under a microscope. Similar care is taken when the ligament is inserted into a unique fixture that allows rotations without handicapping the specimen. The results of complementary fractographic analyses, which were used to identify the strength-limiting flaws and determine the cross-sectional area of the test ligaments, are also presented.

KEYWORDS: ligament, carbon foam, SiC (Silicon Carbide), RVC (Reticulated Vitreous Carbon)

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic foams and carbon foams have been the focus of intensive development and characterization in recent years because of their light-weight, moisture insensitivity and potential for use in applications such as thermal management, filtration, packing and structural applications. Its nearly isotropic properties and its ability to conform to diverse net shapes makes carbon foam a good candidate to be used as a core material in sandwich structures and as 3-D preforms that can be infiltrated with various matrices [1].

Carbon foams are pitch-based porous materials with open cells made up of an interconnected network of solid ligaments, which form the edges of the cell [2]. The foam processing consists of pressurizing pitch or synthetic polymer at different pressures with a gas and then subjecting it to temperature [3]. After the saturation temperature is reached, pressure is increased and held for a certain period of time and then released. Subsequently the foam is stabilized in an oven and carbonized at 900 °C and may also be graphitized at 2700 °C. The processing variables are the foaming temperature, pressure and time. Also, different blowing gases such as Nitrogen, Carbon Dioxide, Argon or Helium can be used. Different foam porosity and cell types are obtained by varying these processing parameters. The properties and the collective behavior of the individual ligaments that make up the cellular structure govern the over all mechanical behavior.

Mechanical tests such as tension, compression and shear have been performed on bulk carbon foam samples to characterize its mechanical behavior. Special fixtures usually are required since carbon foams are brittle and porous. For example, Poisson's ratio of carbon foam (80% of porosity and a pore size of 100 – 150 μm in diameter) was obtained by a non-contact strain measurement optical microscopy method [1]. In this approach an optical microscope with a digital micrometer is used to measure the longitudinal and transverse strains simultaneously. A portable shear test fixture to measure shear stiffness and strength for carbon foam and other porous materials was developed where the shear strain measurements were based on the end rotation of cylindrical specimens

Figure 1. SiC 20 ppi microstructure

Figure 2. SiC 20 cross section

subjected to torsion, as strain gages could not be installed on the porous specimen surface [4]. The strength and fracture toughness of open-cell alumina foams were reported in references [5-6]. The ligament strength was measured by threading a thin steel wire beneath the ligament and connecting it to a tensile load cell. The strength was evaluated assuming a two-end rigidly supported cylindrical beam with a triangular hole subjected to a point load at the center. The fracture toughness was evaluated by three point bending using the edge-notched-beam methodology. Scanning electron micrographs were used to measure the ligament geometry from fractured surfaces. Macroscopic tensile strength of carbon foams with SiC coating was evaluated by diametrical compression of “O”-ring specimens which led to the characteristic strength of 800 Mpa and Weibull modulus of 6.4 [7].

In order to bridge the gap between the microstructure and the global characterization, in the present study, our focus is to develop techniques to determine the tensile strength of single ligaments of carbon foams. Three different designations of reticulated carbon foams are studied. Two of them are 20 and 45 pores-per-inch (ppi) foams coated with SiC by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and the last one is a reticulated vitreous carbon foam (RVC) of 20 ppi.

EXPERIMENTS

Herein, a brief description of the unique procedure developed for isolating a single ligament without damage from the unit cell of the foam microstructure is presented. CrystalBond™ is applied to a piece of foam, approximately 25 mm x 17 mm x 23 mm to secure it on a microscope glass slide. The foam sample is sliced into sections 1.0 – 1.5 mm in thickness using a precision saw and a low-concentration diamond blade. The thin slices are removed from the glass slide by heating them on a hot plate and then cleaned in acetone. This operation is repeated several times until a good ligament is identified. Then, this ligament is cut, cleaned in an ultrasonic bath of acetone and inspected under an optical microscope to ensure its integrity. A typical microstructure and a ligament cross section of SiC 20 PPI foam are presented in Figure 1 and 2 respectively. In general, the ligament has a non-uniform triangular cross section that varies (0.2-0.4 mm) along the length of 0.75 mm to 2 mm.

The selected ligaments are placed in a home-made Teflon™ mold that is designed to mount epoxy end-tabs at both ends of the ligament to allow the transfer of mechanical forces during tensile testing. The mold consists of two mating halves that are held together using a “C” clamp as shown in

Figure 3. Two steel pins with flat tips are placed in the holes of the mold with their flat ends pointing upwards. The top surface is sprayed with a mold release agent to facilitate the removal of the test specimen at the end of sample preparation. Under microscope, the ligament is held in the center gap of the mold using modeling clay to protect its gauge length from being impregnated with epoxy, which is used to cast the end-tabs. The ligament is aligned visually using the mold separation line as a reference. Once the ligament is in its correct position and the gap is totally covered with modeling clay, the mold is filled with a 5-minute curing epoxy and covered with a microscopy glass slide (previously sprayed with mold release agent). After one hour, the specimen is released from the mold. The specimen is cleaned using a lemon-based ultrasonic bath (D-limonene Florida Chemical Co. INC) to remove the modeling clay from the ligament. A picture of a clean specimen ready for testing is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Teflon™ mold for specimen

Figure 4. Specimen for tensile testing

Tensile tests are carried-out at a constant displacement rate of 8.5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{second}$ using a computer-controlled electromechanical testing machine equipped with a 25 lb. -load cell. The load is transferred to the ligament through the epoxy end-tabs. A fixture is used in the testing configuration to ensure the alignment of the load train as shown in Figure 5. Approximately 75 specimens were prepared from each foam type. Prior to testing, a small amount of vacuum grease is applied to the gauge section of the test specimens to redeem fragments and fractured surfaces for subsequent fractographic analysis.

Figure 5. Testing configuration

After tensile testing, both sections of the fractured are ultrasonically cleaned in an acetone bath to remove the vacuum grease. The clean specimens are subsequently coated, with a thin film of gold, to prevent charging

Figure 6. Fracture surface of a SiC 20 specimen

Figure 7. Fracture surface of a SiC 45 specimen

Figure 8. Fracture surface of a RVC 20 specimen

during scanning electron microscopy. Digital scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of every fracture surfaces are obtained and analyzed using a commercially available computer program to determine the cross-sectional area of the fracture plane. Typical SEM images of SiC and RVC specimens of this study are presented in Figures 6 – 8.

RESULTS

The behavior observed in all specimens is a catastrophic one where the load increases as displacement increases and then is followed by a sudden drop-off in load (failure load). . In most cases ligament failed at the gauge section. A linear increase of load as a function of displacement is expected for brittle materials. However, the results show a non-linear, nearly parabolic behavior. A typical load vs. displacement behavior from tensile tests is shown in Figure 9. The non-linear load vs. displacement behavior is attributed to the compliance mismatch. That is, it is due to the existence of the pins, arms, adapter, epoxy end-tabs and the ligament itself. Furthermore, potential curvature of the ligament and some misalignment may also create bending moments, which subjects the ligament to combined loads rather than the simple uniaxial tensile load.

Figure 9. Typical load vs. displacement

All the test results are presented in Figure 10 where each data point indicates the load at failure of a single specimen. It is easily seen that there is scatter in each foam type, with the most variability in SiC 20 ligaments. Note that the behavior of RVC 20 and SiC 45 is similar to each other with RVC 20 ligaments failing slightly higher than for SiC 45. Also, SiC 20, which has lower porosity than SiC 45, fails at significantly higher loads. The load vs. crosshead displacement data of each foam type with the corresponding maximum and minimums are shown in Table 1. The displacement range values reflect the total elongation of the load train, the ligament, epoxy end-tabs, pins, arms, and adapter. The Weibull Modulus and load calculations are presented in Figure 11 and Table 2.

Figure 10. Failure load in each ligament type – all tests

Table 1. Ranges of load at failure and displacements for the three foam designations

Foam Designation	Load at failure range N. (lbs)	Displacement range (μm)
SiC 20	2.25 – 17.15 (0.5 – 3.8)	34 – 207
SiC 45	1.01 – 5.44 (0.22 - 1.21)	25 – 123
RVC 20	1.2 – 5.7 (0.26 –1.27)	39 – 163

Table 2. Weibull Modulus and Load

Foam designation	Weibull Modulus	Characteristic Load (N.)
SiC 20 PPI	2.4259	8.688
SiC 45 PPI	2.8329	3.23
RVC 20 PPI	3.2793	4.3

CONCLUSIONS

In this study a methodology for ligament isolation and specimen preparation for tensile testing evaluation has been successfully developed and implemented. Subsequently 75 isolated ligaments are prepared and tested under uniaxial tensile loading for the three foam designations. More than 40 successful tests are included in the analysis. The data analysis focused on optical microscopy, SEM microscopy and image analysis of ligaments pre and post tensile tests. Typical scatter observed is interpreted through implementing Weibull modulus and characteristic load concept for the three foam designations. The overall results reveal that in RVC 20 and SiC 45 ligaments experienced similar failure loads where as SiC 20 failed at higher loads. Further work is being conducted to understand the influence of curvature and bending on strength interpretations.

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